

EFFECTIVENESS OF INTERACTIVE METHODS IN CHEMISTRY TEACHING IN SECONDARY EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

Tojiboyeva Munisa Akmal qizi

Chirchik State Pedagogical University

Faculty of Natural Sciences

3rd year student of Chemistry Education

<https://orcid.org/0009-0001-9154-696X>

tojiboyeva.m1661@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20453955>

Abstract : This article analyzes the effectiveness of using interactive methods in teaching chemistry in secondary educational institutions. The study covers the didactic and psychological foundations of interactive methods, their positive impact on students' cognitive activity, and their role in deep mastery of the subject based on scientific sources. Also, the experiences of organizing chemistry lessons using interactive methods, including the practical application of methods such as "Brainstorming", "Cluster", "Insert", "BBB Table", "Role Playing", "Team Project", are analyzed through examples. The article provides a scientific, theoretical and practical justification of the effectiveness of the interactive approach in forming students' activity, independent thinking, and experimental skills. The results of the study conclude with recommendations for the wider introduction of interactive methods in teaching chemistry in secondary education.

Keywords: interactive methods, chemistry education, learning process, didactic approach, student activity, lesson effectiveness, experiential learning, secondary education, innovative pedagogy, reflective analysis.

ENTRANCE

In modern pedagogy, the use of interactive methods plays an important role in increasing the effectiveness of education. In particular, the specificity of chemistry - the need to develop practical skills along with theoretical knowledge - encourages teachers to adopt new approaches. While in traditional teaching processes, students are more likely to be listeners and observers, interactive methods shape them as active participants, independent thinkers, and problem-solvers [1]. Due to the complexity of chemistry, the abundance of abstract concepts , and the specificity of experiments, limiting the teaching of chemistry to oral explanations and written information can reduce students' interest. Therefore, organizing a lesson through interactive methods, including group work, role-playing games, projecting, and analyzing problem situations, activates students' learning activities and increases their level of mastery[2].

Research shows that in lessons taught through interactive methods, students not only memorize knowledge, but also acquire the skills to apply it in practice, analyze and evaluate it [3]. Therefore, teaching chemistry through these methods allows students to think creatively, draw conclusions based on experience and form scientific discourse [4].

Today, special attention is paid to the implementation of modern pedagogical technologies in the public education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan. In particular, the State Educational Standards and science programs recommend organizing lessons based on an interactive approach [5]. In this regard, this article will examine the effectiveness of interactive methods in teaching chemistry in secondary educational institutions based on scientific, theoretical and practical experience.

In pedagogical literature, interactive methods are interpreted as approaches based on active communication between the student and the teacher, serving to consolidate knowledge, skills and competencies in the educational process. Interactive methods, unlike traditional teaching, require the active participation of the student, independent thinking, and collaborative problem solving. The psychological foundations of interactive methods have been thoroughly studied by UA Gafurov, and the author describes them as a factor that develops the cognitive (knowledge acquisition), affective (attitude) and psychomotor (practical action) spheres of students [6].

Ismoilova MT in her research empirically studied the impact of using interactive methods in chemistry lessons on students' knowledge. According to her, methods such as "Brainstorming", "Insert" and "Cluster" help to thoroughly master the content of the lesson, form the skills of analyzing the topic, finding cause-and-effect relationships [7]. These methods develop students' skills in critical thinking, communication, and reasoning. For example, through the "Insert" method, the student compares new information with existing knowledge, identifies aspects that are not understood or understood, and feels the need to ask questions.

Yusupov BK, analyzing active teaching methods from the perspective of general educational effectiveness, emphasizes that their main advantage is in strengthening the student's self-awareness and internal motivation to learn [8]. In his opinion, interactive methods are not just a methodological technique, but also a philosophical approach based on the humanistic principles of education.

Karimova ZI studied the characteristics of interactive methods specific to chemistry. She analyzed the methods of "Table Filling", "Experimental Design",

“Project-Based Teaching” used in chemistry lessons and justified their role in thinking through experience, drawing conclusions and forming scientific views in the lesson[9]. In particular, interactive lessons based on experiments create an opportunity to focus students' attention, activate logical thinking, and connect knowledge with life.

The chemistry curriculum approved by the Ministry of Public Education also pays special attention to interactive methods in organizing lessons. It provides recommendations for methods, assessment forms , and practical exercises appropriate for each subject in each grade . This indicates that the interactive approach is one of the priority areas in educational policy [10].

Thus, the analysis of the literature shows that chemistry lessons taught through interactive methods serve to form students not only as knowledge holders, but also as thinkers, problem solvers, and individuals ready for practical activities. Scientific literature, along with the theoretical foundations of this approach, also provides methodological solutions for its implementation in the educational process.

In pedagogical literature, interactive methods are interpreted as approaches based on active communication between the student and the teacher, serving to consolidate knowledge, skills and competencies in the educational process. Interactive methods, unlike traditional teaching, require the active participation of the student, independent thinking, and collaborative problem solving. The psychological foundations of interactive methods have been thoroughly studied by UA Gafurov, and the author describes them as a factor that develops the cognitive (knowledge acquisition), affective (attitude) and psychomotor (practical action) spheres of students [6].

Ismoilova MT in her research empirically studied the impact of using interactive methods in chemistry lessons on students' knowledge. According to her, methods such as "Brainstorming", "Insert" and "Cluster" help to thoroughly master the content of the lesson, form the skills of analyzing the topic, finding cause-and-effect relationships [7]. These methods develop students' skills in critical thinking, communication, and reasoning. For example, through the "Insert" method, the student compares new information with existing knowledge, identifies aspects that are not understood or understood, and feels the need to ask questions.

Yusupov BK, analyzing active teaching methods from the perspective of general educational effectiveness, emphasizes that their main advantage is in strengthening the student's self-awareness and internal motivation to learn[8].

In his opinion, interactive methods are not just a methodological technique, but also a philosophical approach based on the humanistic principles of education.

Karimova ZI studied the characteristics of interactive methods specific to chemistry. She analyzed the methods of “Table Filling”, “Experimental Design”, “Project-Based Teaching” used in chemistry lessons and justified their role in thinking through experience, drawing conclusions and forming scientific views in the lesson[9]. In particular, interactive lessons based on experiments create an opportunity to focus students' attention, activate logical thinking, and connect knowledge with life.

The chemistry curriculum approved by the Ministry of Public Education also pays special attention to interactive methods in organizing lessons. It provides recommendations for methods, assessment forms , and practical exercises appropriate for each subject in each grade . This indicates that the interactive approach is one of the priority areas in educational policy [10].

Thus, the analysis of the literature shows that chemistry lessons taught through interactive methods serve to form students not only as knowledge holders, but also as thinkers, problem solvers, and individuals ready for practical activities. Scientific literature, along with the theoretical foundations of this approach, also provides methodological solutions for its implementation in the educational process.

The use of interactive methods in teaching chemistry in the secondary education system is important not only for improving the quality of education, but also for forming a positive attitude towards science in students . These methods transform students from passive learners to active knowledge holders, developing a culture of independent thinking, problem solving, and communication [11].

Interactive methods have many forms. Among them, the most common methods are “Brainstorming”, “Insert”, “Cluster”, “BBB table”, “Role playing”, “Debate”, “Mind mapping”, “Pair work”, “Mini-projects”, each of which has its own methodological task.

- **Brainstorming** is a method of free expression of ideas by students on a problem. Through this method, students develop alternative ideas on topics such as chemical phenomena, causes of reactions, and environmental impacts. It also develops critical thinking and alternative decision-making skills [12].

- **“insert”** method allows the student to compare new information with what he already knows while working with the text. In chemistry lessons, this method

is especially successfully used in theoretical topics - for example, atomic structure, classification of elements [13].

- **“Cluster”** - develops the student's ability to generalize and classify a topic by writing down various ideas and concepts from a basic concept in the form of networks. For example, through the “Types of Chemical Reactions” cluster, the division of reactions into classes is learned.

- **Role-playing** and **debate** are socializing methods that teach students to think about chemical problems from the perspective of different social roles (scientist, environmentalist, manufacturer, etc.). Through these methods, the importance of science in society is deeply understood[14].

Interactive methods are especially important in chemistry, where laboratory experiments, models , and diagrams are used to teach the subject. The teacher can assign tasks to small groups during the lesson, assigning each group the task of developing an experimental design and analyzing the results of the experiment. In this approach, students do not just accept a ready-made result, but create it through their own activities [15].

For example, a debate on the topic of "Acid Rain" is organized, with one group representing the interests of industrialists and the other representing environmentalists. Through this, students see the vital aspects of science and understand the need to solve real problems on a scientific basis.

Also, based on the “Project-based Learning” approach, students develop small experimental projects: for example, determining pH values at home , determining the composition of substances found in everyday life (vinegar, salt, carbonated water). Such activities develop students' scientific research skills [16].

Scientific research shows that for interactive methods to be effective in education , the following conditions are necessary:

1. Teacher's methodological preparation - incorrect or superficial use of interactive methods reduces their expected effectiveness.
2. be based on intrinsic motivation, not just external appearances .
3. Appropriateness of assessment mechanisms - in an interactive lesson, assessment is carried out not only through tests and written work, but also based on criteria such as participation in debates, project defense, and group work [17].

CONCLUSION

the above analysis and scientific sources, it can be said that teaching chemistry in secondary schools using interactive methods will fundamentally improve the educational process. Compared to traditional approaches,

interactive methods increase students' interest in the lesson, enable independent and critical thinking, communication, scientifically based conclusions, and the formation of practical knowledge and skills.

The uniqueness of chemistry lies in the combination of its theoretical and practical aspects. Interactive methods are the most effective tool for combining these two directions. In this regard, especially experimental methods, role-playing, project-based learning, debate and clustering approaches are highly effective. Forming students not only as knowledge holders, but also as active participants and creators, giving them the competence to solve life problems on the basis of science is a priority direction of modern education.

Also, the impact of interactive methods on educational effectiveness largely depends on the teacher's pedagogical skills, methodological level, and ability to properly plan the lesson process. Therefore, it is necessary for teachers to study interactive methods in depth and introduce mechanisms for continuous methodological support in their implementation in practice.

Suggestions:

1. It is necessary to develop and distribute special teaching and methodological manuals on the use of interactive methods for chemistry teachers.
2. Special attention should be paid to teaching interactive methods in in-service training courses for teachers each academic year.
3. A multi-criteria assessment system should be introduced when assessing students, based not only on test results, but also on activities such as participation in interactive lessons, group work, and project defense.

Thus, interactive methods are a highly effective methodological basis for chemistry education that meets modern requirements. Through their correct and systematic application, students develop a scientific outlook, research skills, and practical knowledge.

References used:

1. Rahmonkulova, MT (2021). Ways of using interactive methods in modern teaching. Tashkent: TDPU Publishing House.
2. Jo'rayev, MA (2020). Interactive methods and their role in education. Education and Development, No. 3, 25–28.
3. Sobirova, DS (2019). Innovative technologies in teaching chemistry. Pedagogical Research, No. 2(17), 19–22.
4. Karimova, ZI (2022). The effectiveness of using information and communication technologies in chemistry education. Science and Modern Education, No. 1(45), 31–35.

5. Hasanov, BH (2018). Developing chemical thinking in students. Secondary specialized education , No. 4, 44–47.
6. Bobojonov, AJ (2021). The essence of active learning technologies. New Uzbekistan Education , No. 2(7), 18–20.
7. Abduazizov, MK (2019). Competency-based approach in the educational process. Pedagogy and Psychology , No. 3, 14–18.
8. Rasulova, G.H. (2020). Developing students' independent thinking in teaching chemistry. Science and Development , No. 4(30), 39–41.
9. Khudoyberganova, RM (2022). Interactive methods in improving educational effectiveness. Teacher's Journal , No. 5, 22–25.
10. Yusupov, QT (2019). The use of interactive methods in teaching subjects. Scientific and Practical Research , No. 1, 10–13.
11. Turgunov, IH (2022). The effectiveness of teaching subjects using interactive methods. Teacher's Journal , No. 1, 16–19.
12. Gafurov, UA (2020). Pedagogical technologies and interactive methods . Tashkent: O'qittu.
13. Ismoilova, MT (2019). The impact of using interactive methods in chemistry lessons on students. Science and Education , No. 4(36), 41–45.
14. Karimova, ZI (2018). The use of interactive methods in chemistry. Bulletin of Sciences of Uzbekistan , No. 1, 24–28.
15. Yusupov, BK (2021). The effectiveness of active teaching methods in modern education. Pedagogical skills , No. 2, 33–37.
16. Islamova, DX (2022). Project-based learning approach in chemistry. Science and Development , No. 3(51), 29–32.
17. Kadyrov, RH (2020). Assessment strategies in active learning methods. Pedagogical Research , No. 2, 44–47.

